

To what extent do design choices while creating the first specification of an F1 car at the start of a regulation cycle influence the performance of the car?

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Abstract

This research paper assesses the impact of initial design choices on the first specification of a Formula 1 car at the start of a regulation cycle. In order to determine the impact these decisions have on car performance, extensive research was done on aerodynamic and mechanical principles and a case study upon Red Bull from 2009-2013 was used to demonstrate how design philosophies stemming from those first decisions evolve throughout a regulation cycle. By posing this question as a topic, I will also discuss the impact of upgrades and whether continuous development matters greater than initial decisions. Analysis of distinct choices at the design stage will allow me to draw conclusions upon the question posed and understand the methods of development used by teams in the past. Furthermore, to aid my analysis, I have provided visual graphics from a virtual wind tunnel simulation of an F1 car of my own design which inherits key features from the Red Bull case study.

1 Regulations

In order to delve into car designs, we must understand the need for regulations, and what regulations in Formula 1 seek to achieve. Regulations are a set of rules that car designers must follow in Formula 1 to legally compete. It's where the name Formula 1 comes from - "Formula" meaning the same set of regulations every team has to follow. The regulations are there for the primary purpose of safety. Introductions in the past such as the "Halo", and crash structures all contribute to safety in the sport.

More recently, in order to align with global views, regulation changes have pushed the sport to a greener direction. The 2014 regulations saw the substitution of the 2.4l V8 engine configuration with a 1.6l V6 hybrid engine.

F1, like any sport, requires money to run and grow. Some regulations introduced by the FIA make the sport more competitive; thus more interesting, gaining viewership and marketability. Regulation changes have been directed at certain teams to remove an advantage, such as the banning of the Dual-Axis Steering(DAS) system implemented by Mercedes in 2020. Mercedes being the dominant team in 2020(winning 13/16 total races), failed to retain the driver's title in 2021(albeit controversially), and only won the constructors' by 28 points. The 2021 season consequently gained the highest viewership in Formula 1's history.

Figure 1: Graphic showing track domination between the Mercedes W11(2020, in turquoise) and the Mercedes W12(2021, in white) at the Austrian Grand Prix. (F1 Tempo, 2021)

The innovation of DAS was that it allowed the driver to increase the camber of the tires to the optimal angle for straight-line speed by using the steering wheel in an untraditional sense. When this was removed, Mercedes' 2021 car(W12) was hindered on the straights, as shown in Fig. 1.

1.1 An Engineer's Role with Regulations

One may argue that constant regulations restrict innovation in Formula 1, making it a predictable competition where the performance difference between teams is minimized and there is little room for groundbreaking advancement. However, regulations inspire engineers to innovate around the restrictive laws, and search for loopholes and grey areas. Their job is to interpret the regulations in their own way to improve. "Part of my job, perhaps even the part I relish most, involves working out what the regulations actually say, as opposed to what their intent is."(Newey A., 2017)

2 The F1 Design and Development Process

The Formula 1 car is born through a complex process that requires hundreds of people and thousands of hours. In order to better understand the coming case study, it is important to discuss how the car is made and developed throughout the season.

2.1 Initial Design Process

In Formula 1, there are two types of teams: Customers, and Manufacturers. Manufacturers are teams which build their own engine, or purchase help from a technical partner to do so. Customer teams have contracts with manufacturers to purchase their engines. See Table 1.

While making an efficient engine is a difficult challenge and costs millions, it allows teams to develop their engine(layout) to suit their chassis, rather than vice-versa. This allows more freedom in development - the first major choice teams have to face.

The design of the F1 car is then broken down into 3 major sections - Aerodynamics, Powertrain and Mechanical. These are the biggest contributors to performance in a race car. The designers have to ensure that not only does the car follow the regulations, but also suit both drivers' wants. An example of this is Lewis Hamilton requesting the seating position of the W15 shifted back(illustrated in Fig. 2) - allowing him to have a better "feel" of the car's behaviour during cornering.

Team	Type	Supplier
Red Bull Racing	Manufacturer (with Partner)	Honda
Visa Cashapp Racing Bulls	Customer	Honda
Mercedes-AMG Petronas	Manufacturer	Mercedes
McLaren	Customer	Mercedes
Aston Martin	Customer	Mercedes
Williams	Customer	Mercedes
Scuderia Ferrari	Manufacturer	Ferrari
Haas F1	Customer	Ferrari
Kick Sauber F1	Customer	Ferrari
Alpine	Manufacturer (with Partner)	Renault

Table 1: Engines in Formula 1

Figure 2: The Mercedes' shift 10cm backward on driver seating position, as requested by Lewis Hamilton. (Giorgio Piola, 2023)

2.1.1 Design Process Overview

Figure 3: Wind Tunnel Configuration. (Ogawa, A. et al, 2008)

The car is first designed through Computer Aided Design(CAD) and undergoes iterative testing using Computational Fluid Dynamics(CFD). At latter stages, a 60 percent scale model of the car is tested with a wind tunnel, which allows physical measurements of pressures at each area of the car. The car is evaluated and improved upon after testing until the near-final model is tested by the drivers using the Driver-In-The-Loop simulator. This completes the design of the first specification of the car. During these first steps, crucial decisions are made which will have integral effects on car performance and

behaviour. I seek to assess the extent of the influence that these selections have on car performance.

2.2 The Performance Contributors in Motorsports

While we will look at more specific examples in a case study later, to truly assess the impact of decisions in a regulation context, it is useful to know the general aim of design and important principles that define choices for performance. The impact of these decisions will be my primary focus in this paper.

2.2.1 Downforce Vs Drag Reduction

The largest determinants of performance across a car are downforce and drag reduction. Ideally, the perfect car would be one with maximum downforce and minimal drag, but an increase in downforce (mostly) increases drag. This decision typically leans to the downforce side. These two terms will be used often in this paper, so it is important to understand what they mean.

2.2.2 Drag Reduction

There are two types of drag on a body. Skin-friction drag and induced drag. Skin friction drag is self-explanatory, caused by friction of the air molecules against the body of the car, increasing proportionally with the square of velocity. Induced drag (pressure drag) is when flow separates behind a body, leading to an extremely low pressure region behind the body. Air travels to the region, further increasing drag as it slows and increases friction on the body.

Drag reduction is defined by the equation:

$$C_d = \frac{D}{\frac{1}{2}\rho V^2 A} \quad (1)$$

Drag coefficient equation - where D is the drag force, and A is the frontal area. In a controlled environment such as a wind tunnel, we can set the velocity and density. If we rearrange the equation to make F_D the subject, we can see that F_D and A are directly proportional. Hence increasing the frontal area increases drag. When requiring higher downforce production, the optimal angle of attack is usually around 17 degrees, thereby increasing frontal area and increasing drag - one of the typical trade-offs required between downforce and drag.

Another trade-off between downforce and drag is also made as increasing downforce can be done by increasing thickness or camber of the aerofoil shape - this in turn increases boundary layer thickness and thus causes increased drag.

2.2.3 Downforce Derivation

Figure 4: The aerofoil shape - the basic example of downforce generation, a shape used aplenty in motorsports, particularly on wings.

Downforce is the generation of negative lift through the motion of air causing a pressure differential across a surface (Katz J., 2005). This pressure differential leads to a force as air attempts to move from high to low pressure. The pressure differential is created by air flowing on one surface at a greater velocity than the other. This is illustrated in Fig. 4, where we have the basic example of the aerofoil.

We can observe that air is displaced more by the bottom surface than the top ($d_2 > d_1$). According to the continuity law, this displacement, or loss of flow area, must lead to an increase in velocity (MIT, 1997):

$$A_1 v_1 = A_2 v_2 \quad (2)$$

A_2 is less than A_1 , as the displacement d_2 is greater than d_1 . This means that v_2 is greater than v_1 .

So we now know that there is increased velocity on the lower surface. This leads to lower pressure due to **Bernoulli's Equation**:

$$p_1 + \frac{v_1^2 \rho}{2} = p_2 + \frac{v_2^2 \rho}{2} \quad (3)$$

Where ρ is the density of the air. We can rearrange this to get:

$$p_2 = p_1 + \left(\frac{v_1^2 \rho}{2} + \frac{v_2^2 \rho}{2} \right) \quad (4)$$

As we know from Eq. (2) that $v_2 > v_1$, we know that p_2 will be less than p_1 and results in lower pressure on the bottom than the top, and hence a downforce.

2.2.4 Increasing Downforce

Downforce is increased with an increase in angle of attack, until the "stalling angle":

$$C_l = 2\pi\alpha \quad (5)$$

Where C_L is the lift coefficient, and α is the angle of attack in radians.

Downforce is also increased with increased area of the wing:

$$L = \frac{C_l A \rho v^2}{2} \quad (6)$$

Where L is the lift force, A is the area of the wing, v is the velocity, and ρ is the density.

2.2.5 Aerodynamic Downforce and Performance

Figure 5: Forces on a tire during cornering phase. Note that drag and normal forces have been ignored in this scenario, but would be present. (Motorsportsmagazine, 2019)

To understand why downforce is helpful, consider the forces on a car taking a corner (Fig.5). Cornering forces are created at the contact patch between the tire and the road. Friction-like forces are strongly affected by the vertical force applied on the tires (Eq.6) and are limited by some maximum friction coefficient μ . When we exceed this maximum friction coefficient (AKA the limit of tire adhesion), the car slides.

$$F_F = \mu F_N \quad (7)$$

F_F is frictional force, F_N is Normal force, and μ is the maximum friction coefficient. We know that if we increase the downforce, the total resultant normal force will increase ($F_N = W + F_D$, where F_D is downforce) hence increasing the frictional force of the tire on the road, and enhancing grip.

While an increase in mass also increases F_N , the acceleration of the car will be hindered as there is more force required per unit mass to accelerate the car ($F = ma$). Downforce is a spectacular phenomenon in that it increases the limit with zero added mass.

Because downforce has such a large impact in cornering speed, drag reduction is secondary in race car design. This is a pattern which we can observe through history (Fig.6 and 7). The Indianapolis Speedway consists of a track in an oval shape. The qualifying is determined by average speed across the lap. Before the 60s, the primary aim for designers was to reduce drag. We can see the one-lap record improved at a steady rate until the late 1960s, where it suddenly started to improve at a much faster rate. The late 1960s was the time in which aerodynamics began to be implemented. There was another jump in 1972, where the first efficient use of front and rear wings occurred. The graph below shows exactly why downforce has a much greater effect than drag reduction - even on tracks where there are plenty of straights.

Figure 6: Graph to show Indianapolis 500 average speed over time. (Indianapolis Motor Speedway, n.d.)

Figure 7: Graph with added trend-lines to showcase the impact of aerodynamic downforce on car performance at the Indy 500. The black line is extrapolated to show where we would be if not for aerodynamic downforce.

So designers tend to increase aerodynamic downforce on the car over drag. The aim is to get the greatest average speed over the track, and there is much more contribution to this in the corners with larger downforce, even if the drag on straights is increased as a result.

2.2.6 An Aside on Vortices

In aerodynamics, there is a common phenomenon known as vortices. Vortices are usually generated whenever there is a pressure differential across two surfaces to generate lift/downforce. The air attempts to move from high to low pressure, and can essentially "spill" over surfaces to equalise the pressure, leading to tip vortices(Katz, 2005). Vortices can also be formed by extruded shapes that oppose the direction of air travel.

Figure 8: Graphic to show the formation of wing tip vortices. Notice the high pressure air "spilling" over the tip of the wing. This leads to strong rotating vortices flowing downstream.

Vortices are essentially a region in a fluid which flows around a central axis line. Pressure is lowest at the centre and rises progressively with distance from the centre. They can provide both negative and positive effects on the car.

Positive effects on the car are when vortex generators are used to generate a turbulent boundary layer. The circular motion of the vortices energises the flow and as such prevents boundary layer separation, reducing induced drag. This principle is used on golf balls - the dimples generate small vortices and thereby greatly increase the range of the ball. Vortices can also act as barriers to protect areas from dirty airflow, such as vortices placed on the sides of the floor to protect the underfloor airflow against dirty airflow from the tyres.

Figure 9: Graphic to show the beneficial effects of vortices on a golf ball(ResearchGate, 2011).

However, when it comes to F1 car design, the negatives of vortices are far more important to consider. Vortices in the wrong places can lead to two major negatives that increase drag and decrease downforce - a designer's nightmare. If a vortex trails the beam or rear wing, the low pressure region behind the car can greatly increase induced drag. Furthermore, if vortices were to disturb the clean airflow beneath a wing or the underfloor, it can slow airflow and thereby decrease downforce(Eq. 4). It is greatly important to analyse where vortices are generated in the car to produce effective and not detrimental upgrades.

3 Case Study: Red Bull 2009-2013

3.1 Context

The 2009 Formula 1 regulations saw the first radical aerodynamic rule changes in Formula 1. Red Bull as a team were coming into their fourth season in Formula 1, being one of the youngest teams on the grid. Having had a disappointing 2008 season in which they finished below their sister team, Toro Rosso, in 2009, they look to flip the script, with the help of Adrian Newey (a 12-time constructors' championship winning designer).

3.2 Regulations

The key things to note from the regulations are listed below:

1. Front wings are made wider to a width of 1800mm - encompassing the full tyre-to-tyre width.
2. Front wings are also made lower to the ground from 150mm to 75mm.
3. Rear wings are made to be only 750mm in width (a 75 percent decrease)
4. Rear wings are made 150mm higher than previous regulation.
5. Diffuser at the rear of the car was moved rearward by 330mm.
6. Barge boards, winglets, and turning vanes all banned.
7. Kinetic Energy Recovery System (KERS) is introduced. This device takes thermal energy generated during the braking phase from the tyres and engine and stores it in a battery to be used by drivers at will.

Figure 10: Drawings to depict the regulation changes made between 2008 to 2009.

The aim for these regulation changes was to encourage overtaking.

By making the front wing wider and lower to the ground, the front wing's downforce levels are increased (Eq. 6). The reduction of height also makes the wing less sensitive to airflow of a car in front. The front wing generating a high proportion of the downforce is key to improving overtaking opportunities, as the front wing is the first part of the car to interact with the dirty air. If high downforce levels are still achieved behind another car, this can improve ease of overtaking.

Figure 11: Typical front wing lift coefficients (as tested on Simscale CFD)

On top of this, the rear wing being made higher and narrower decreases the overall downforce level of the car and makes downforce at the rear much lower. This leads to a more unstable car under braking, but most importantly, the volume of the wake from the car ahead is reduced and at a greater height so when a lower front wing is behind it receives less disturbed flow. Another reduction in downforce is seen with the decrease in diffuser length.

The final key introduction was the Kinetic Energy Recovery System (KERS). KERS was extremely beneficial to certain teams and drivers who managed it correctly - the KERS giving drivers an extra 60kW of power, which could potentially contribute to a lap-time improvement of around 0.2-0.3 seconds. The key consideration to take into account is the added weight of the KERS. KERS is an optional device, so many teams thought the increase in weight of KERS was not worth the additional power.

3.3 Red Bull's Initial Design Philosophy

Red Bull's initial design included many features that were unique to their car, with head designer Adrian Newey allowed freedom to experiment with the new regulations.

The first thing Red Bull introduced was the pull rod rear suspension. Red Bull was the only team on the grid to implement this suspension design, with every other team utilising the push-rod method. There are two options for suspension - pull rod and push rod. Both rods connect the top of the wheel-base to the torsion spring housed in the chassis. The pull rod is mounted on a low point on the chassis connected to a higher point on the wheel rim, whereas the push rod is mounted the vice-versa (Kanal, S., 2023). The advantages of using a pull-rod suspension was that by being mounted lower, suspension items such as springs and rockers are also mounted lower, hence achieving a lower centre of gravity,

bringing more stability to the car. The mounting being lower also results in a tighter rear bodywork design, allowing for a much more advanced "coke-bottle profile".

However, as the pull-rod setup is mounted lower it is integrated within the bodywork and engine components of the car. This makes it much harder to access and therefore setup ranges are restricted, hence on extremely bumpy circuits where an extremely soft suspension is required, Red Bull would be likely to struggle.

Figure 12: Drawing of the RB5 rear pull rod suspension. The short red arrow points to the pull rod, and the curved red arrow depicts the airflow over the exposed upper wishbone leading to the beam wing.

The next consideration was the overall shape of the car. The "coke-bottle" shape is often used in F1. The top side of the coke-bottle was widened with a much narrower rear end. Red Bull's car was much narrower than any other car on the grid in order to feed maximum airflow to the rear for increased rear downforce to counteract the regulation change. The reduction in overall size increased rear downforce and greatly reduced drag (Eq. 1 - frontal area A reduced).

Figure 13: RB5 top down view. Notice the narrowing of the chassis toward the rear. The shape looks somewhat like a coke-bottle from this view, hence the name.

The design of the new diffuser was crucial in order to make the most out of the shortened area. With the diffuser now starting level with the rear axle, turbulent air from the rear tyre squish was being injected into the diffuser. In order to prevent this, wings were attached to the rear brake duct to create vortices that would act in the opposite direction to the squish vortices, hence providing a barrier between the diffuser and this dirty air.

Figure 14: Visualisation of the effect of tyre squish. Strong counter-rotating vortices from the airflow being disrupted by the tyre disturb the airflow under the diffuser, reducing downforce.

Figure 15: CFD Simulation of a tyre. Note the red airflow paths crossing over each other and curling after contact with the wheel - these are the strong counter-rotating vortices.

Another key characteristic Red Bull prioritised in order to gain the most out of their diffuser was creating a low-pressure field at the back of the car. This helps draw the flow through the diffuser as air moves from a higher pressure area to a lower one. This is simply done using the beam wing (the secondary lower rear wing seen on all F1 cars). Red Bull were initially going to use push rod suspension - however, this would corrupt the flow to the beam wing and drastically reduce its efficiency. As aforementioned, the decision was made to switch to pull-rod suspension. The clear airflow path meant that no suspension items would create turbulent airflow and decrease the velocity of the airflow - as we know decreased velocity reduces downforce levels (Eq. 4), this must be avoided. The upper wishbone was also allowed to become exposed, and designed with an aerodynamic profile that links to the beam wing, further energising flow and increasing downforce.

The front wing itself featured innovative ideas including a triple-element base wing. By consisting of 3 elements, some of high pressure flow from top surface of wing bleeds to lower surface of next flap which energises the airflow, decreasing risk of stalling under high angles of attack. This allows the running of the car's wing at much higher downforce levels (Eq. 5).

Figure 16: Graphic showing multi-element wing airflow advantages.

Finally, the nose was made higher in order to force more air under the car to make the most out of the small diffuser area, and accelerate more air under the car in order to reduce drag. The drag is

reduced as the speed under the car is always higher than the speed over the car in order to maintain a pressure differential to provide downforce - again, a reference to Eq. 4.

3.4 2009 Development Timeline

As testing in Jerez begun, it was immediately noticed that 3 teams had an intriguing rear design, one which would increase their downforce drastically. The design itself looked illegal, but the FIA confirmed its legality in a meeting. There was a loophole in the regulations which Red Bull did not catch, allowing for the infamous double diffuser.

3.4.1 The Double Diffuser

The loophole in the regulations allowed for the creation of a secondary diffuser at the back of the car with much more freedom of around 300mm against the 175mm Red Bull had been restricted to. This secondary diffuser essentially increases the overall volume of the diffuser which leads to lower pressure under the car and increased downforce - as we already know from Equations 4 and 6. The second diffuser was fed by an airflow channel from holes in the underfloor of the car, which is where the controversy comes in, as the regulations state there can be no holes in the reference or step planes. However, this was considered a hole in the transition between the two planes, bypassing the regulations(Newey, A. , 2017).

Figure 17: The double diffuser theory. The airflow is imaged in green, and flows under the curved component of the underfloor, which is the secondary upper diffuser. The primary diffuser which all teams had is located below this, the body part below the green airflow.

The increase in downforce was seen as a huge benefit to those who implemented it, and therefore many presumed Red Bull would be on the back foot for the season's start, with only Brawn, Toyota and Williams discovering the design.

3.4.2 Initial Design Results

While it was true that Red Bull didn't immediately have race-winning pace, the design choices made by Newey in pre-season were not futile. At the opening round in Australia, Vettel managed P3 in qualifying, only shy of both Brawn cars. Red Bull seemed to look the only team who could compete against Brawn, even without a double diffuser.

While their car had a strong relative pace, the execution by the drivers was inconsistent and luck was not on Red Bull's side, issues for Vettel in Bahrain and a crash in Australia led to 0 points on the board on that side of the garage. In order to jump to firm frontrunners it was clear the double diffuser would need to be implemented, providing a crucial pace gain for Red Bull.

3.4.3 Chinese Grand Prix

The next race was at Shanghai. Each track has its own characteristics, and Shanghai is a demanding track on grip and downforce, but also has an extremely long back straight which makes up of the majority of the final sector. This leads to diverging setups - some prioritise high downforce, whereas some prioritise high drag. As discussed in sections 1 and 2, one cannot be increased drastically without the other declining.

The Red Bull team decided to opt for a low drag setup - this decision was made as Red Bull was aware that teams that had equipped the double diffuser at the start of the season would have an advantage in downforce and would be inclined to choose a higher downforce setup. If Red Bull went down the same path, they would ultimately lack the same levels of aerodynamic grip as the others due to the absence of a double diffuser. Hence the decision to prioritise drag reduction - the correct decision to make.

In a dry qualifying, Vettel claimed pole position while Webber settled for P3, and in an all wet race the duo transformed the 1-3 into a 1-2, earning the team's first victory.

Figure 18: Podium celebrations at the 2009 Chinese Grand Prix.

This proved to Red Bull that their starting package provided good foundations to build upon.

3.4.4 Red Bull's Double Diffuser Implementation

In order to begin in-season development, a double-diffuser was rushed onto the car at the Monaco Grand Prix. However, the fit of the parts was poor. As aforementioned, Newey focused on narrowing the rear bodywork drastically, leaving little room for a double diffuser. Suspension items and gearbox placement meant it was tricky to create airflow to the second diffuser. While it did provide a marginal gain, the boost was insufficient, with Brawn winning the race once again. The initial choice to tightly package everything in the rear to make it as narrow as possible had hindered development here.

Figure 19: Red Bull's rear double diffuser design. Note the light blue arrows on the underfloor, which indicate the airflow feed entry to the upper diffuser.

For Silverstone, a more considered version of the double diffuser was brought to the car with great difficulty as the suspension and gearbox were designed around the single version. After rearrangement of these key components, the wind tunnel promised strong gains of up to two tenths per lap which were proven in the race. Silverstone's high-speed nature rewarded a high-downforce setup, which Red Bull achieved with the second version of their diffuser, and a second 1-2 was claimed.

It was now clear Red Bull had the advantage over Brawn on pure pace, and was not dependent on the nature of the track to claim victory. The initial aerodynamics considerations allowed for high levels of downforce which were further improved upon by the inclusion of a double diffuser.

Red Bull went on to claim another 1-2 in Germany and performed well for the rest of the season. But by the time Red Bull caught up in car performance, they were too far behind in the standings to catch Brawn in the championship.

Figure 20: Points throughout the season for Brawn GP and Red Bull Racing. Notice the gain in gradient after Round 9 at the British Grand Prix, where Red Bull's double diffuser was introduced.

Figure 21: Red Bull’s qualifying delta to Brawn each race. Note the downward trend. Plots below the x-axis indicate races where Red Bull were faster than Brawn. Notable races: Round 3(China) where the Red Bulls made the correct setup decision and Round 8 (Silverstone) where the double diffuser was brought in.

3.5 2010 Development Timeline

After the 2009 season, Red Bull had established themselves as a race winning team, capable of beating established champions such as McLaren and Ferrari. Red Bull look to pick up where they left off, and end the season as winners of the championship.

3.5.1 Winter Development

The regulations were unchanged coming into 2010. Now, they had the challenge of redesigning the double diffuser, gearbox and suspension so everything creates one cohesive design, something they could not develop out of during the 2009 season’s duration.

In order to gain the most downforce out of a diffuser, the length was increased(Eq. 6) to the wheel centre line. This required an essential rearrangement of the lower wishbone member of the rear suspension, connected at a higher height to accommodate the larger diffuser space. This would have marginally increased the height of the CoG, but the overall gain in downforce is a much greater benefit.

Figure 22: Simple schematic showcasing the suspension lift on the RB6..

Figure 23: Further CAD to showcase in 3D the lower wishbone movement.

The already narrow design of the gearbox coupled with the upper part of the double diffuser allowed a very deep and wide upper profile (increased A , Eq.6) that linked to the beam wing, leading to a much lower pressure region under the car and faster airflow, with the low pressure beneath the beam wing acting as a suction for the air through the diffuser.

Figure 24: The changes to the beam wing for the Red Bull RB6. Notice the much wider and deeper upper profile (Sutton, M. 2011).

There were many smaller refinements to the front of the car such as the greater exaggeration of the V-shape.

Another area which was focused upon was the exhaust outlet positioning. Exiting the exhaust into the diffuser was banned in Formula 1, but would have seen a massive gain in downforce as fast and hot gases from exhaust energise the airflow into the diffuser, increasing velocity of air, thereby creating even lower pressure and increasing downforce (Eq 4.) However, with the introduction of the double diffuser, there was a possibility that the exhaust gases can be exited into the side of the upper diffuser without technically breaking the rules.

Figure 25: Exhaust exit positioned for airflow to upper part of double diffuser.

3.5.2 Initial Results

While the car produced strong results in the wind tunnel, at testing the rear tyres were destroyed after as little as two laps. Both Webber and Vettel complained of oversteering and instability. The issue was pinpointed immediately however - the Red Bull had a curled-up floor toward the rear of their car which led to local downforce generation, but also pressure loss towards the rear, as the air doesn't follow to the rear of the car but ended up in the rear-wheel squish area, energising this turbulent flow and potentially destabilising the diffuser. These curls were removed and the car immediately behaved as expected.

Figure 26: Annotated CAD model to show the part of the floor which was removed from the RB6.

At the first round in Bahrain, Vettel took pole. It was clear the car was much faster than before. Unfortunately, Vettel had to slow due to a broken spark plug. Come round 2 at Australia, the team were plagued with wheel nut issues and bad luck struck again, with Vettel retiring and Webber finishing 9th.

3.5.3 Front-Rear Interconnected Suspension

The suspension of a Formula 1 car is extremely important to performance. Springs in the car ensure that the tyres remain in contact with the track despite bumps and curbs which may unsettle the car. Maximising contact with the track surface is crucial for maintaining grip. The stiffness of these springs

can be tuned to be softer for "bumpier" circuits or stiffer for "smoother" circuits. Ideally, the track would be as smooth as possible. This means that the car does not move in the vertical direction at all, thus not affecting any aerodynamic effects on the car.

However, as speed is built up, we know downforce increases by Bernoulli's principle. This means the car sinks into the ground the faster the car goes. For this particular regulation cycle, the front wing is much larger than the rear wing, thus producing much more downforce and leading to the front of the car "sinking", the car pitching forward.

Red Bull's first upgrade of the season addressed this problem by introducing front-rear interconnected suspension(FRIC).

Figure 27: Front Rear Interconnected Suspension diagram.

The setup used actuators in connection with central heave springs to have a differential between the rear and front suspension stiffness, allowing for the rear to be looser while the front remains stiffer or vice versa - the springs would act to create a stable platform. This was particularly useful as the front suspension moving up and down on track is connected to the rear suspension by the system, which counteracts the change by the front by altering both suspensions' stiffnesses accordingly. For example, if the front started to sink relative to the rear, the electronic sensors would detect this movement and increase the stiffness of the front springs whilst decreasing the stiffness of the rear springs, moving to counteract the change. This creates a constant stable aerodynamic platform, which means no fluctuations in ride height and hence no unpredictable fluctuations in downforce.

Other teams treated the front and rear suspension independently, so changes in front ride height could not be constantly changed by the rear as there was no connection between them.

Figure 28: Simplified diagram showcasing the feedback and control loop of FRIC.

It proved an extremely beneficial upgrade, with Red Bull claiming a 1-2 at the race. Red Bull saw further success throughout the season, with aid of a major upgrade in Spain addressing minor refinements across numerous components.

The season ultimately finished with a close title decider between Alonso and Vettel for the Drivers' Championship. The Constructors' was decided much earlier, with Red Bull sealing the double at the final round in Brazil.

3.6 2011 Development Timeline

Red Bull had now proved their might in claiming a double world championship, both the Drivers' and Constructors' crowns, beating well established teams and making Vettel the youngest world champion of the sport ever. With success comes expectation, and they looked now to retain the championship in 2011.

3.6.1 Winter Development

After 2010, the FIA banned the double diffuser. The challenge posed by this was to claw back some downforce even without the crucial device. Newey decided to develop the exhaust blown diffuser.

Development began by increasing the rear ride-height slightly so the entire underfloor could act as a gentle diffuser, being at an angle to the horizontal ground. The only problem with this is that the tyre-squish area's losses is more likely to disrupt the flow under the car with more area for vortices to spread.

So Newey decided to combine these two ideas, and try to blow the exhaust air toward the tyre contact patch, preventing the interference of this dirty air with the underfloor aerodynamics and increasing velocity of airflow due to energy of exhaust air. There is an inherent challenge in this as it is extremely difficult to channel the exhaust to such a low point.

Figure 29: Red Bull new exhaust placement

The exhaust air would flow into a vortex creating fence first introduced on the RB5. This vortex creating fence together with highly cambered wings would manipulate a downwash flow field into the squish area. Interestingly, these small wings would generate lift - while this may seem counter-intuitive, the marginal loss in downforce from this is lesser than what would have been lost had the squish volume

remained large. Wings that generate lift create a downwash flow field, which allows the air to be directed in the correct direction toward the contact patch. Wings that generate downforce create an upwash flow field, as shown by the front wing CFD below. A simple explanation is by Newton's third law - as we know the wings produce downforce, there is a force acting down on the wing produced by the air. Therefore, there must be an equal and opposite force pushing up on the air - creating an upwash flow field.

Figure 30: Example of an upwash flow field created by a typical front wing - note the green particle traces under the wing flowing upward.

This design worked brilliantly to generate downforce, but it needed to work throughout the entire cornering phase, as the exhaust only blows when the driver is pressing the throttle. It would need to work also on corner entry during the braking phase to maximise performance.

So Red Bull asked Renault(their technical partner in engine supply) to develop a method for the exhaust to be blowing all the time. Renault managed to do so with blending of positioning cylinders and altering ignition timing.

By this season, many of the teams had now decided to implement KERS. Red Bull included. While weight was no longer much of a concern, the aerodynamic compromise upon restructuring the bodywork to fit the batteries could be a problem. Newey had the idea of placing it between the engine and the gearbox, leading to no change in aerodynamic setup as this was essentially an empty space. Many teams shied away from this placement as it could lead to a dangerous overheating cycle that could cause a fire. Red Bull ensured the battery was protected with necessary precautions, and made sure cooling channels flowed into the area.

3.6.2 Season Performance Results

The car was rapid, especially with the use of the new exhaust system, providing levels of downforce no other car had aside from McLaren who had a similar idea working to a lower effect.

One problem was that the KERS on the Red Bull was overheating frequently. The drivers were told to switch it off at times and the extra pace was lost. However, due to the great performance the aerodynamic package even without KERS the car still claimed victories.

There weren't many upgrades to the car itself throughout the season other than minor reliability adjustments. Red Bull ran away with the championship, having dominated from the get go. They finished over 150 points ahead of any other team and won 12 out of 19 races.

Figure 31: Cumulative Points per Race for Red Bull Racing and McLaren-Mercedes in 2011

Figure 32: McLaren(2nd place constructor) time gap to Red Bull at each qualifying.

3.7 2012 Development Timeline

Work on the 2012 car began during the 2011 season, with Red Bull having a large advantage over the other teams that they decided to shift focus onto the next season.

3.7.1 Pre-Season Development

After a "one-horse" championship in 2011, the sport was deemed "boring" by media and fans booed Red Bull on the podium as they were sick of seeing the same team on top over and over again. And so the FIA decided to take action, and added a new regulation that banned the current method of "hot-blowing" the exhaust.

Red Bull can only merely attempt mitigation of this regulation with other updates. They decided to further narrow the rear bodywork which was currently in the same shape as it were on the RB5(2009 car) and they angled the end even further down. The exhaust would now exit into the rear bodywork section, providing some airflow to the beam wing. While this solution worked while the exhaust was on(under throttle), the regulation banned the method which allowed exhaust on under braking, creating a real problem in braking stability with a loss of downforce.

Figure 33: Red Bull 2011(top) vs 2012(bottom) car design

In order to improve overall rear downforce, Newey deemed that the small wings mounted on the rear brake duct could be improved further by lengthening the chord(Eq. 6, A increased) and increasing the camber(curvature) of the wing. However, due to the pull-rod setup chosen at the start of the cycle, the lower wishbone and trackrod were physically in the way and would disrupt the flow. Hence, the suspension legs were rearranged onto the same plane as the driveshaft and enclosed in a singular hollow structure, which could be shaped as an additional wing leading to further downforce gains.

Figure 34: Brake ducts and suspension wing profile design.

3.7.2 Initial Results

After pre-season testing at Jerez, it was clear the Red Bull's pace advantage had completely disappeared. After removing the exhaust-blown diffuser, which Red Bull had designed their underfloor around, it was difficult to completely alter that philosophy and extract the same performance compared to other teams which had never designed their car for the blown diffuser in the first place. Other teams had innovations that were based on the normal diffuser design and hence were quicker in that respect.

Hence Red Bull took a step back comparatively in the field. They qualified 5th and 6th at the opening round in Melbourne and seemed to be 3-4 tenths behind the leaders of Ferrari and McLaren.

A further disadvantage with the banning of the exhaust blown diffuser is that it rendered Vettel's current driving style futile. Vettel had the tendency to turn the car in very late and hard which demanded an extremely grippy rear end. Webber preferred a more traditional style of braking in the straight line and then easing into the corner, which meant he wasn't affected as much by the loss of rear grip.

3.7.3 Rear Tyre Squish Duct

The team continued to struggle for the first rounds of the season, scoring low points finishes and 4th in the pecking order.

After further CFD and wind tunnel analysis of the previous 2011 model, Red Bull noticed that under large cornering loads, the deformation of the tyre led to a larger squish volume which can cause flow separation behind the tyre. Flow separation is extremely detrimental to a car as it leads to a high amount of induced drag (less air in one area so more pressurised air flows into the region, dragging against the body). It also leads to a huge loss in downforce as air behind a wing becomes filled with turbulent vortices and no low pressure region to suck out air hence slowing air beneath wing and thereby a loss of lift force (Eq. 4).

Figure 35: Typical tyre wake. Note the circular path of the air traces after contact with the tyre - these are turbulent vortices. There are also point of flow separation just behind the tyre, where red flow lines indicate air flowing into the section.

In order to manage these turbulent vortices from the wake of the wheel, a duct was introduced on the floor, right ahead of the rear tyres. The duct on the floor, while reducing local downforce, directs air to the inboard side of the tyre contact patch, shielding the underfloor and diffuser from the turbulent vortices produced by the tyre squirt.

Figure 36: Red Bull's rear tyre squish duct.

Additionally, Renault managed to get more flow into the exhaust on entry, increasing downforce further.

And so the upgrade was introduced in the Monaco Grand Prix. The Monaco Grand Prix is a circuit that demands high downforce, with little to no straights, downforce was crucial - this would be a test of the new upgrade. The upgrade passed with flying colours, as Mark Webber ended up claiming victory at Monaco, with Vettel finishing fourth, giving Red Bull their first victory of the season.

3.7.4 Exhaust Pulses

However, there were still further improvements to be had in terms of the exhaust blowing the beam wing. After the Monaco Grand Prix, it was noticed that "exhaust pulses" led to losses of downforce upon corner exit. These exhaust pulses are caused by the operation of the cylinders in the engine itself. The engine mechanism consists of cylinders that move up and down in cycles. When each cylinder's exhaust valve opens, a wave is created which travels down to the end of the pipe and creates a vortex that flows downstream into the exhaust, thus momentarily reducing downforce.

In order to showcase the impact of the pulses I have created a simulation in Python using sine waves and transformations to simulate the impacts of the pressure wave numerically.

Figure 37: A simulated cycle of the impact of exhaust pulses before and after the solutions, using matplotlib and numpy libraries in python.

The update to solve this required two steps. The first was to reduce the strength of the shock waves which Renault managed by fitting a resonator in the exhaust system to absorb and reflect the wave. The second was to raise each side of the exhaust exit valve so the vortex is contained.

Figure 38: Diagram showcasing airflow of the exhaust. Notice where the yellow arrows originate from, the sides of the exit are raised.

These updates were introduced at Valencia, which created a more predictable car and aided in rear grip at a demanding street circuit. Vettel led the race comfortably before an alternator failure and Webber managed a P4 after qualifying 19th with a hydraulics issue, an incredible performance considering the circumstance.

The new updates brought Red Bull right to the forefront, after Valencia Vettel dominated Singapore, Japan, Korea and India, clawing back the points gap to Alonso and Ferrari.

Figure 39: Red Bull qualifying gaps to pole position in 2012.

The combination of Vettel and the updated car ultimately beat Alonso in a nail-biting season finale at Brazil, winning the Drivers' crown. The Constructors' trophy was secured a round earlier at Austin, wrapping up another double for Red Bull - 3 in a row.

3.8 2013 Development Timeline

With the last year of the regulations dawning upon Red Bull, only one question remained - can they take four consecutively?

3.8.1 Pre-Season Development

The 2013 season saw the end of the regulation cycle, so many teams devoted time to research for their 2014 car development rather than focusing on the 2013 car development, as the new cycle of regulations looked to be set for years to come and featured integral changes such as the brand new hybrid turbo engines.

As such, not many upgrades came to any cars, and most development was done in the pre-season.

The RB9 for 2013 was much the evolution of the RB8. There were small tweaks almost everywhere for minor gains in performance. One of the interesting things that was tweaked was the link from the

chassis to the beam wing. The connection was now moved to the top of the beam wing, hence freeing and cleaning airflow beneath the beam wing to aid in further downforce increase.

The RB9 also featured an S-duct, originally introduced by Sauber into F1. This was a duct that collected slower air under the nose (air under the nose is inherently slower due to the up sweep) and transported it through a NACA duct which released it rearward on top of the car's nose - towards the side pods where it would have a lower impact on overall downforce losses than being released toward the underfloor. At the underfloor section it is much more crucial to have fast-flowing air (Eq. 4), as this is where the majority of the car's downforce is generated from.

Figure 40: CFD of an F1 s-duct. Notice the acceleration of the air (red → blue) when it travels through the duct, and the remaining air under the car continuing at a fast speed (dark blue)

3.8.2 Season Performance

When it came to the season itself, Red Bull already had an advantage from being the fastest car at the end of 2012. On top of this, the additional upgrades brought further increased their speed, and any minor upgrades brought by other teams in pre-season were not enough to compete. As mentioned earlier, other teams did not invest much into the 2013 season due to the upcoming regulation changes. Hence, Red Bull ran away with both championships, winning 13/19 grand prix, and Vettel winning 9 grand prix in a row.

Figure 41: Constructors' Standings per race in 2013, showcasing the extent of Red Bull's dominance.

4 Evaluation: How Significant was the Initial Design Phase for Red Bull?

4.1 Positive Impacts of Initial Design Decisions

1. Narrow Gearbox and Enhanced Coke-Bottle Effect

At the start of the season, Newey designed a narrow gearbox to allow an enhanced coke bottle effect. Over a year later, the narrow design enabled an aerodynamic profile that linked the rear chassis to a beam wing which could accelerate airflow to a larger extent at the rear of the car - one of the major winter updates coming into the 2010 season.

2. Exhaust-Blown Diffuser

The Exhaust-blown diffuser was one of the major updates that led to Red Bull's success in 2011. This innovation was ingenious, and worked extremely well for Red Bull - arguably the main reason their car secured both championships that year. While it may seem that any other team could have thought of this and easily implemented it, many tried and failed. McLaren struggled with reliability issues and overheating due to the exhaust blowing generating heat near critical components, whilst Ferrari could not develop an off-throttle blowing method that would work, unlike the engineers at Renault (Red Bull's engine provider). The fact is, Newey's compact and efficient car design was crucial to direct airflow to the diffuser - he had planned from the early stages to include the exhaust blown diffuser, thus the entire rear floor was designed on this, rather than simply designing a diffuser to work with the current floor as other teams did.

3. Tyre Squish Vortices

Combatting the tyre squish vortices in 2011 pre season was easily done by forcing some of the exhaust air into a vortex creating fence first introduced in Red Bull's 2009 car - simply fuelling this component from the initial design stage with energised air led to increased performance.

4. Pull-rod Rear Suspension

The pull-rod rear suspension implemented by Newey had many advantages in that it cleared flow to the beam wing and allowed the narrowing of the rear of the car, further accelerating airflow, the overall shape of the chassis resembling a tear-drop - often recognised as the perfect aerodynamic shape to reduce drag. As such, the suspension was left much unchanged throughout the 5-year regulation cycle - unlike other teams such as Ferrari which underwent a change from push to pull rod at rear during the 2012 season.

4.2 Negative Impacts of the Initial Design Decisions

1. Double-Diffuser

One of the biggest struggles of Red Bull's 2009 season was the difficulty of implementing an effective double-diffuser. The enhanced coke-bottle profile implemented at the start of the season meant that suspension and gearbox elements were physically in the way of a double diffuser. It was only after a crucial rearrangement and 2 attempts that a double diffuser could be put on the car, and this was again redone for the 2010 season.

2. KERS

The only way to implement KERS without a major rearrangement of component positions set at the design stage or restructuring of crucial bodywork was to place it in between the engine and the gearbox - this led to it being highly unreliable and "dead weight" in the car, often being switched off in the Grand Prix slowing them down rather than providing extra power.

3. Brake Duct Wings

The pull-rod rear setup led to difficulty in implementing wings near the rear brake ducts in 2012

pre-season, as the suspension members would corrupt the flow to the wings, leading to insufficient production of downforce.

4.3 Unaffected Updates

These are upgrades where the initial design decisions had no effect on:

1. FRIC

The innovation of the Front-Rear Interconnected Suspension (FRIC) was ingenious, with the idea inspiring Mercedes to create an updated model in 2014, part of the reason for their dominance in the hybrid era. The design itself would remain unaffected by the rest of the car design, the suspension being an independent member and additional electronic components for the system being small in size.

2. Rear Tyre Squish Duct

The rear tyre squish duct brought in 2012 was a simple update that required the removal of floor material, unaffected by earlier decisions. However, one could argue that the duct would not be required had the car been designed for no exhaust-blowing in the first place.

3. Exhaust Pulse Reduction

This update was done mainly inside the engine itself, requiring only the raising of the sides of the exhaust exit valve in terms of aerodynamic changes. This meant that the design could have been implemented on other cars if they had the correct resources and research.

4.4 Conclusion

To conclude, while there were some updates which were largely unaffected by the overall chassis design choices - such as FRIC or the exhaust pulse resonators, many of the initial design choices had lasting impacts on performance or the ease of introducing upgrades. Another example that could be discussed is Red Bull's struggle in the 2012 season - due to the banning of exhaust-blown diffusers. While this wasn't a direct flaw as a result of early decisions, it highlights how this development path was shaped by the design they had created from those first decisions.

Ultimately, upgrades rely on parts which are already present on the car - testing and analysing performance on track from the first specification reveals weaknesses which engineers target to develop and optimise. If the engineers decide a new concept or component is necessary (such as the decision to include a double-diffuser in 2009), they must work with the original framework to implement this. There is always an impact from first specification of the car.

This is further displayed by teams' own treatment of new regulation cycles. For example, in 2013 (the final year before a major regulation cycle), many teams stopped development on their current car to focus on next season's machine. This showcases the importance the teams themselves place on getting the original specification right. In many cases, when the base concept is strong, the team is set for success. Take Mercedes in 2014 for example, or Red Bull in 2022 - both having earned multiple world championships by implementing an efficient design philosophy from the outset.

Therefore, the answer to the question posed at the start of this paper: initial design choices significantly influence the performance of a car throughout a regulation cycle.

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